

Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of *N*-lactosylated isothiobiurets

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Manuscript received 13 March 2007, accepted 18 September 2007

Abstract : A series of new 1-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -*D*-lactosyl-5-aryl-4-isothiobiurets have been synthesized by the interaction of hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -*D*-lactosyl isocyanate and aryl thiocarbamides and their antimicrobial activity were tested. The synthesized compounds have been characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, IR, NMR and mass spectral studies.

Keywords : Lactosyl, aryl thiocarbamides, antimicrobial activity.

Recently, we have reported a method for synthesis of hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl isocyanate¹ by the interaction of hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl bromide² and lead cyanate. Sugar isocyanates are important intermediate in synthesis of various ureido linked derivatives³.

Urea, thiourea and their derivatives not only show strong antibacterial activity but also versatile reagent in organic synthesis⁴. Several sugar isothiobiurets are reported and tested for their biological activity^{5,6}. In view of the applications of S and N-lactosylated compounds in medicinal chemistry and in many other ways⁷⁻⁹, we herein report the synthesis of 1-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -*D*-lactosyl-5-aryl-4-isothiobiurets (**3a-g**) by the interaction of hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl isocyanate (**1**) and aryl thiocarbamides (**2a-g**) (Scheme 1).

Results and discussion

1-Hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -*D*-lactosyl-5-aryl-4-isothiobiurets (**3a-g**) (Scheme 1) are prepared by the condensation of hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -*D*-lactosyl isocyanate (**1**) with aryl thiocarbamides (**2a-g**) in chloroform for 3 h. The solvent was distilled off and the resultant sticky residue was triturated with petroleum ether to afford titled compounds (**3a-g**). The products were found to be desulphurised when boiled with alkaline lead acetate solution. The specific rotation $[\alpha]_D$ was measured in chloroform. The purity of the products were checked by TLC and R_f values were recorded.

IR spectra^{10,11} of the products show the characteristic absorption of lactose in the range of 900–910, 1000–1100 cm^{-1} . ¹H NMR spectra¹²⁻¹⁴ of the products show characteristic of lactosyl protons at δ 5.6–3.7 ppm. Mass

spectra^{15,16} show characteristic of lactose unit at m/z 619, 559, 331, 169 and 109.

where, R = (a) Phenyl, (b) *o*-Cl-phenyl, (c) *m*-Cl-phenyl, (d) *p*-Cl-phenyl, (e) *o*-tolyl, (f) *m*-tolyl, (g) *p*-tolyl

Ac = $-\text{COCH}_3$

Scheme 1

Antimicrobial activity :

Antibacterial activity :

The compounds (**3a-g**) were screened for their antibacterial activity against various pathogenic bacteria such as *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *P. vulgaris*, *Pseudomonas* using cup plate method¹⁷ at a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ in DMF using co-trimazine (25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) for bacteria. The compounds **3a**, **3d**, **3e**, **3g** showed higher and other compounds showed moderate activity against used bacteria.

Antifungal activity :

The compounds **3a-g** were also screened for their antifungal activity against *A. niger* and *Penicilline* using the cup plate method at a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ in DMF using standard griseofulvine (10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). The

Note

compounds **3a**, **3d** and **3g** exhibited higher activity against *A. niger*, while **3d**, **3e** and **3f** are sensitive towards *Penicilline*. The other compounds were less to moderately active against used fungi.

Experimental

Optical rotations¹⁸ $[\alpha]_D$ measured on a Equip-Tronics digital polarimeter model no. EQ 800 at 31 °C in CHCl_3 . IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrum RXI (4000–450 cm^{-1}) FTIR spectrometer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker DRX-300 NMR spectrometer operating at 300 MHz in CDCl_3 solution with TMS as an internal reference. Mass spectra were recorded on a Micromass Quattro II mass spectrometer.

1-Hepta-O-acetyl-β-D-lactosyl-5-aryl-4-isothiobiurets (3a-g) :

Condensation of hepta-*O*-acetyl-β-D-lactosyl isocyanate (**1**) (0.005 M, 3.3 g) and aryl thiocarbamides (**2a-g**) (0.005 M) in chloroform (20 ml) was carried out on boiling water bath for 3 h. The solvent was evaporated and sticky residue obtained was triturated with petroleum ether (60–80°) to afford the title compounds (**3a-g**). The products were crystallized from ethanol. The purity of the products were checked by TLC, % yield, m.p., optical rotation, elemental analysis and R_f values, which are shown in Table 1.

(**3a**) IR (KBr) : 3484 (N–H), 2965 (Ar–H), 1751 (C=O), 1374 (C–N), 1231 (C–O), 906 and 1051 (characteristic of lactose), 1169 cm^{-1} (C=S); ¹H NMR (CDCl_3 ppm) : δ 7.44–7.26 (5H, m, Ar–H), 6.33 (1H, s, N–H), 5.35 (2H, s, NH), 5.10–3.76 (14H, m, lactose unit), 2.18–1.96 (21H, m, 7COCH₃); mass (m/z) : 813 (M⁺), 619, 559, 331, 169 (Found : C, 50.08; H, 5.13; N, 4.83; S, 3.90. Calcd. for C₃₄H₄₃O₁₈N₃S; C, 50.18; H, 5.28; N, 5.16; S, 3.93%).

(**3d**) IR (KBr) : 3417 (N–H), 1751 (C=O), 1365 (C–N), 1232 (C–O), 906 and 1053 (characteristic of lactose), 1168 cm^{-1} (C=S); ¹H NMR (CDCl_3 ppm) : δ 7.42–7.20 (4H, m, Ar–H), 8.06 (1H, s, NH), 6.15 (2H, s, NH), 5.38–3.77 (14H, m, lactose unit), 2.19–1.96 (21H, m, 7COCH₃); mass (m/z) : 847 (M⁺), 619, 331, 109 (Found : C, 48.12; H, 4.90; N, 4.87; S, 3.74. Calcd. for C₃₄H₄₂O₁₈N₃SCl : C, 48.17; H, 4.95; N, 4.95; S, 3.77%).

(**3g**) IR (KBr) : 3437 (N–H), 3170 (Ar–H), 1751 (C=O), 1371 (C–N), 1232 (C–O), 904 and 1052 (characteristic of lactose unit), 1169 cm^{-1} (C=S); ¹H NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : δ 8.05 (1H, s, N–H), 7.27–7.11 (4H, m, Ar–H), 6.58 (2H, s, N–H), 5.30–3.77 (14H, m, lactose unit), 1.96–2.19 (21H, m, 7COCH₃); mass (m/z) : 827 (M⁺), 619, 331, 169 (Found :

C, 50.71; H, 5.34; N, 4.90; S, 3.74. Calcd. for C₃₅H₄₅O₁₈N₃S : C, 50.78; H, 5.44; N, 5.07; S, 3.86%).

Table 1. Characterization data of 1-hepta-*O*-acetyl-β-D-lactosyl-5-aryl-4-isothiobiurets (**3a-g**)

Compd.	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	$[\alpha]_D^{31}$ (in CHCl_3)	R_f	Found (Calcd.) %	
					N	S
3a	86.20	123	+39.21 (c, 1.02)	0.68	4.83 (5.16)	3.90 (3.93)
3b	66.35	109	+19.60 (c, 1.02)	0.72	4.75 (4.95)	3.65 (3.77)
3c	80.56	125	+28.30 (c, 1.06)	0.84	4.81 (4.95)	3.60 (3.77)
3d	73.45	120	+20.00 (c, 1.00)	0.60	4.87 (4.95)	3.74 (3.77)
3e	84.74	119	+70.00 (c, 1.00)	0.91	4.92 (5.07)	3.80 (3.86)
3f	78.04	135	+20.20 (c, 0.99)	0.85	4.77 (5.07)	3.68 (3.86)
3g	92.14	128	+58.82 (c, 1.02)	0.81	4.90 (5.07)	3.74 (3.86)

Satisfactory C, H analysis were obtained for all compounds.

The required aryl thiocarbamides¹⁹ and hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl isocyanate¹ were prepared by the method described earlier.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to RSIC, CDRI, Lucknow for providing spectral data. Authors also thanks Principal, Dr. S. G. Bhadange for providing necessary facilities.

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